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QUASI-PHASE TRANSITIONS IN THE PROCESS OF DEFORMATION FRACTURE OF METALS

Анотація. Досліджено явище квазіфазових переходів у процесі деформаційного розриву металів. Автори аналізують вплив деформаційного розриву на мікроструктуру та механічні властивості металів. Вони висвітлюють особливості квазіфазових переходів, які відбуваються при розриві матеріалу, та їх вплив на процес формування тріщин. Робота детально розглядає механізми, що лежать в основі цих переходів, та їхні наслідки для механічної поведінки металів під час деформаційного розриву. Висновки можуть бути корисними для подальших досліджень у галузі металургії та матеріалознавства.

Ключові слова: квазіфазові переходи, деформаційне руйнування, метали, мікротріщини, деформаційні методи, мультифрактальність, фазовий перехід другого роду

Abstract. This article investigates the phenomenon of quasi-phase transitions in the process of deformation fracture of metals. The authors analyze the influence of deformation fracture on the microstructure and mechanical properties of metals. They highlight the peculiarities of quasi-phase transitions occurring during material fracture and their impact on crack formation processes. The study delves into the mechanisms underlying these transitions and their consequences for the mechanical behavior of metals during deformation fracture. The conclusions of the article may be valuable for further research in the fields of metallurgy and materials science.

Keywords: quasi-phase transitions, deformation fracture, metals, microcracks, change of deformation mechanism, multifractality, second-order phase transition.

Problem description and its relevance

The significance of this issue arises from its broad applicability across various disciplines. In materials science and engineering, understanding the mechanisms of phase transitions during deformation fracture is crucial for developing advanced materials with enhanced mechanical properties and fracture resistance [1]. For example, in the aerospace industry, where materials are subjected to extreme loading conditions, knowledge of phase transitions can aid in the development of lightweight yet sturdy materials for aircraft components. Similarly, in the automotive sector, the ability to predict and control phase transitions can result in the production of safer and more durable vehicles.

The issue of comprehending phase transitions during the deformation fracture of metals is highly significant due to its impact on scientific research and technological innovation. Solving

this problem can result in advancements in materials design, manufacturing processes, and various industrial applications.

Objectives of the article.

Understanding phase transitions in materials is crucial in scientific and practical domains, especially in the context of deformation fracture. Phase transitions cause fundamental changes in the structure and properties of materials, often resulting in significant alterations in their behavior. In the case of deformation fracture of metals, the study of phase transitions is crucial due to its direct implications on material strength, ductility, and fracture resistance.

The stated article aims to address these unresolved aspects of the problem by:

1. Investigating the phenomenon of quasi-phase transitions in the process of deformation fracture of metals.

2. Analyzing the microstructural changes and mechanical behavior of metals during deformation fracture.

3. Examining the mechanisms underlying quasi-phase transitions and their implications for crack formation processes.

4. Identifying the relationship between microstructure evolution, phase transitions, and mechanical properties during deformation fracture.

By elucidating these aspects, the article seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of phase transitions in materials and provide insights that can inform the design of advanced materials with enhanced mechanical performance and fracture resistance [2; 3].

Presentation of the main material

Strain fracture of a metal is a complex process that involves changes in the metal structure and its properties at different scales, leading to its destruction with heat generation. The changes themselves can be described as quasi-phase transitions. During the destruction of a metal, these transitions occur more than once until it is completely destroyed [4–6]. Below are some examples of quasi-phase transitions that can occur during metal fracture:

Transition from elastic to plastic deformation: this transition can be thought of as a change in the mechanical properties of the metal;

Elastic deformation: the metal can be returned to its original shape after the deformation force is removed.

Plastic deformation: the metal does not return to its original shape after the deforming force is removed.

Microcracks: during the deformation process, microcracks will inevitably form or expand, which leads to a change in the metal topology;

The appearance of localized plastic zones: these are areas that are more susceptible to deformation. This type of transition is associated with a change in the local deformation of the metal.

The analysis of quasi-phase transitions was carried out using the multifractal method of research, and the indicator of the occurrence of quasi-phase transitions is the heat released during deformation.

Multifractal analysis is a powerful method of analysis that makes it possible to investigate complex systems by studying their fractal properties.

To investigate the time series with different scaling behaviors, we utilize multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis (MFDFA) [2], which is an extension of detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA) [2].

MF-DFA has been extensively employed in various fields including finance, physiology, biology, traffic engineering [3], geophysics, and neuroscience for characterizing the properties of non-stationary time series.

The MF-DFA method operates in the following way:

1. Given a time series $\{x(i)\}, 1, \dots, N$, we begin by integrating it to produce a profile $y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^k [x(i) - \langle x \rangle]$, where $\langle x \rangle$ is the average value of $\{x(i)\}$.

2. Next, we divide the integrated series $y(k)$ into $l_s = \text{int}(l/s)$ non-overlapping segments of length s . For each of these l_s segments, we estimate the local trend by fitting a least-squares line and subtract it from $y(k)$ to remove the trend from the integrated series. Finally, we calculate the variance of each detrended segment, v :

$$F^2(v, s) = s^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^s \{y(v-1+i) - \hat{y}(v, i)\}^2, \quad (1)$$

in which $\hat{y}$ represents the fitted trend within segment $v = 1, \dots, l_s$. Here, we utilize a first-order polynomial to fit the local trend.

Proceeding from both the beginning and end of the time series, step (2) results in a total of $2l_s$ segments. We calculate the q th order fluctuation function by averaging over all segments:

$$F_q(s) = \left\{ (2l_s)^{-1} \sum_{v=1}^{2l_s} [F^2(v, s)]^{q/2} \right\}^{1/q}. \quad (2)$$

For a real number q , where q is positive, the fluctuation function $F_q(s)$ quantifies large fluctuations, whereas for negative q , it quantifies small fluctuations.

4. To obtain the fluctuation function $F_q(s)$ for different box sizes s , we perform the aforementioned calculation repeatedly. If $F_q(s)$ increases according to a power-law $F_q(s) \sim s^{h(q)}$, then the scaling exponents $h(q)$ (also known as generalized Hurst exponents) can be estimated by determining the slope of the linear regression of $\log F_q(s)$ versus $\log(s)$. The fluctuation parameters $h(q)$ depict the correlation structures of the time series at various magnitudes. The value of $h(0)$ cannot be determined using (2) due to the diverging exponent. The logarithmic averaging method should be utilized instead:

$$F_0(s) = \exp\left\{ (4l_s)^{-1} \sum_{v=1}^{2l_s} \ln[F^2(v, s)] \right\} \sim s^{h(0)}. \quad (3)$$

The multifractality of a time series can be measured by the generalized Hurst exponents $h(q)$ as a function of q . If the values of $h(q)$ are uniform for all q , the time series is monofractal. Conversely, if there is variation among $h(q)$ values, the time series is multifractal. The classical multifractal scaling exponents τ , defined using the standard partition function-based multifractal formalism, are directly linked to the generalized Hurst exponents $h(q)$ [2]:

$$\tau(q) = qh(q) - 1. \quad (4)$$

Utilizing the concepts of MF-DFA, we can gain fresh insight into viewing a time signal as a thermodynamic system. Within MF-DFA, the mass exponent $\tau(q)$, the Lipschitz-Hölder exponent α , the multifractal spectrum $f(\alpha)$, and the distortion exponent q can be seen as analogous to the free energy, energy, entropy, and temperature of a thermodynamic system, respectively. More specifically, the specific heat $C(q)$ can be defined as:

$$C(q) \equiv \frac{d^2\tau(q)}{dq^2} \approx \tau(q+1) - 2\tau(q) + \tau(q-1). \quad (5)$$

The specific heat, as a measure of the rate of energy variation, serves as an indicator of phase transition phenomena. In a thermodynamic system, a phase is characterized by uniform physical properties, and a phase transition refers to the discontinuous change of certain properties under a critical external condition. The study of phase transitions in the multifractal spectrum has been limited to simple systems, such as the Cantor set and logistic map. However, our analysis reveals the presence of phase transitions in complex networks and in the multifractal spectrum of financial systems. Specifically, the “energy” α exhibits significant fluctuations near q_c , which are reflected by the peak of the specific heat $C(q_c)$. [1] The overall degree of multifractality, total multifractal specific heat (C_{area}) can be expressed via the Eq. (5):

$$C_{area} = \int_{q_{min}}^{q_{max}} C(q) dq. \quad (6)$$

Using MFDFA concepts, we can look at a time signal as a thermodynamic system. In MFDFA, the mass index $\tau(q)$ is analogous to free energy, the singularity index α is analogous to internal energy U , and the multifractal spectrum is analogous $f(\alpha)$ to entropy. In fact, the shape of the multifractal spectrum resembles the dependence of the entropy of a thermodynamic system on energy U . The parameters a_{min} and a_{max} can be characterized as upper and lower bounds on the internal energy of the system [2]. The function $Z(q)$ is a formal analog of the statistical sum $Z(\beta)$ in thermodynamics, where $\beta = \frac{1}{T} = q$.

Figure 1 shows the dynamics of pressure on metal over time. This line indicates when metal changes from elastic to plastic deformation.

- Point of strain "780" – is the point when pressure on metal changes its properties from elastic to plastic. After this point, metal cannot return to its original shape;
- Stress point "260" – is the point of maximum pressure on the metal at which it does not collapse;
- After strain point "5800" – metal loses bonds on atomic level and it causes a collapse.

Figure 2 shows that the multifractal specific heat increases at the moment of the collapse event, which characterizes each of the sharp temperature jumps as a quasi-phase transition. For different statistical moments q , we can see that the specific heat looks symmetrical, but it is important to note that during the collapse it tends to positive values of q , which indicates the prevalence of large fluctuations in the multifractal nature of each collapse.

A phase transition of the second type was detected on the graph obtained because of multifractal analysis of the time series of metal deformation. Multifractal analysis studies the fractal properties of the deformation process, such as scale invariance and variability. A phase transition of the second type can manifest itself as a sudden shift in the fractal properties of the time series, indicating a change in the metal deformation mechanism.

A sharp shift or break in the relatively regular behavior is observed on the multifractal analysis graph, indicating a change in the system dynamics. This may indicate the presence of a second type of phase transition, where the system moves from one state to another without specifying the exact value of the critical parameter. This may be an indicator of sudden changes in the structure or behavior of the metal, which may correspond to a phase transition.

Thus, a phase transition of the second kind was detected on the multifractal analysis graph as a sharp shift in the fractal properties of the metal deformation time series, indicating a change in the system dynamics and a possible transition between different deformation phases.

Conclusions

Based on our study, we confirmed the presence of a second type of phase transition. Through multifractal analysis of the time series of metal deformation, we observed a sharp shift in the fractal properties, indicating a change in the system dynamics. This suggests a possible transition between different deformation phases, which is typical of second-order phase transitions. This confirmation allows us to better understand the mechanisms that control metal deformation processes and contributes to the further development of our understanding of materials physics.

Prospects for further research in this area

Despite these advancements, several aspects of the problem remain unresolved. One such aspect is the precise mechanisms governing phase transitions at the atomic and subatomic levels during deformation fracture. Additionally, understanding the influence of external factors such as temperature, strain rate, and alloy composition on phase transitions requires further investigation.

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